

Denitrification in *Sinorhizobium meliloti*

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Abstract

Denitrification is the complete reduction of nitrate or nitrite to N₂, via the intermediates nitric oxide (NO) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), and is coupled to energy conservation and growth under O₂-limiting conditions. In *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*, this process occurs through the action of the *napEDABC*, *nirK*, *norCBQD* and *nosRZDFYLX* gene products. DNA sequences showing homology with *nap*, *nirK*, *nor* and *nos* genes have been found in the genome of the symbiotic plasmid pSymA of *Sinorhizobium meliloti* strain 1021. Whole- genome transcriptomic analyses have demonstrated that *S. meliloti* denitrification genes are induced under micro-oxic conditions. Furthermore, *S. meliloti* has also been shown to possess denitrifying activities in both free-living and symbiotic forms. Despite possessing and expressing the complete set of denitrification genes,

S. meliloti is considered a partial denitrifier since it does not grow under anaerobic conditions with nitrate or nitrite as terminal electron acceptors. In the present paper, we show that, under micro-oxic conditions,

S. meliloti is able to grow by using nitrate or nitrite as respiratory substrates, which indicates that, in contrast with anaerobic denitrifiers, O₂ is necessary for denitrification by *S. meliloti*. Current knowledge of the regulation of *S. meliloti* denitrification genes is also included.

Keywords: denitrification, FixLJ, micro-oxic conditions, nitric oxide, NnrR, *Sinorhizobium meliloti*.

Abbreviations used: CRP, cAMP receptor protein; FNR, fumarate and nitrate reductase regulatory protein.

Introduction

The bacterial order Rhizobiales of the Alphaproteobacteria includes the genera *Allorhizobium*, *Azorhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Rhizobium* and *Sinorhizobium* (*Ensifer*), among others. They are Gram-negative soil bacteria collectively referred to as rhizobia with the unique ability to establish an N₂-fixing symbiotic association with legume plants through the formation of a new differentiated organ called the nodule on the roots and on the stems of some aquatic species [1,2]. The initiation of the rhizobia–legume symbiosis is a highly specific and complex developmental process in which both partners undergo differentiation in a concerted way [3]. Within the nodules, rhizobia transform into specialized cells, the so-called bacteroids, which synthesize the enzyme nitrogenase, which fixes atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) through its reduction to ammonia. Rhizobia have developed mechanisms to sense and adapt to changes in O₂ concentrations prevailing in the environment. Hence many rhizobia species possess a branched electron-transport chain, in which the terminal oxidases have different affinities for O₂ in order to survive under different environmental O₂ conditions [4]. In the microaerobic environment of the root nodule, rhizobia use the high-affinity cytochrome *cbb₃* terminal oxidase to support the highly ATP-demanding nitrogen-fixation process [4]. When O₂ is limiting, some rhizobia species are able to switch from O₂ respiration to using nitrate to support ATP production by denitrification. During this process, nitrate (NO₃⁻) is reduced into nitrite (NO₂⁻), nitric oxide (NO), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and N₂ through the action of the nitrate, nitrite, nitric oxide and nitrous oxide reductase enzymes, encoded by the *nar/nap*, *nir*, *nor* and *nos* genes respectively [5].

Many rhizobia species have genes for enzymes of some or all of the four reductase reactions for denitrification. In fact, denitrification can be readily observed in many rhizobia species in their free-living forms, in legume root nodules or in isolated bacteroids [6,7]. *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*, the soya bean symbiont, is considered the model organism for studying rhizobial denitrification, as it is the only rhizobial species able to denitrify under both free-living and symbiotic conditions. In *B. japonicum*, denitrification is dependent on the *napEDABC*, *nirK*, *norCBQD* and *nosRZDYFLX* genes that encode a periplasmic nitrate reductase, a copper-containing nitrite reductase, a *c*-type nitric oxide reductase and a nitrous oxide reductase enzyme respectively [8]. In *B. japonicum*, a sophisticated regulatory network, consisting of two linked regulatory cascades, the FixLJ/FixK₂-NnrR and the RegSR/NifA systems, co-ordinates expression of denitrification genes in response to low O₂ conditions and the presence of nitrate [9]. Under symbiotic conditions, *B. japonicum* denitrification contributes to NO and LbNO (nitrosyl-leghaemoglobin) production within soya bean nodules in response to hypoxia [10,11].

Sinorhizobium meliloti is a rhizobial species which establishes symbiotic N₂-fixing associations with plants of the genera *Medicago*, *Melilotus* and *Trigonella*. *S. meliloti* has been shown previously to possess denitrifying activities in both free-living and symbiotic forms [12–14]. In fact, genes of the denitrification pathway, enabling the complete

reduction of NO_3^- to N_2 , are present in the *S. meliloti* genome. Furthermore, transcriptomic analyses have shown that *S. meliloti* denitrification genes are induced in response to O_2 limitation [15]. However, and despite possessing the complete set of denitrification genes, *S. meliloti* has been considered a partial denitrifier due to its inability to grow under anaerobic conditions with nitrate or nitrite as terminal electron acceptors. In our studies, we have demonstrated for the first time that *S. meliloti* is able to grow under micro-oxic conditions using nitrate or nitrite as respiratory substrates.

Denitrification genes in *S. meliloti*

Inspection of the *S. meliloti* 1021 genome sequence shows a composite architecture, consisting of three replicons with distinctive structural and functional: a 3.65 Mb chromosome and two megaplasmids, pSymA (1.35 Mb) and pSymB (1.68 Mb) [16]. pSymA contains a large fraction of the genes known to be specifically involved in symbiosis and genes likely to be involved in nitrogen and carbon metabolism, transport, stress and resistance responses that give *S. meliloti* an advantage in its specialized niche [17]. A 53 kb segment of pSymA is particularly rich in genes encoding proteins related to nitrogen metabolism, including a complete pathway for denitrification [17]. Among them, the *napEFDABC*-type (*sma1232*, *sma1233*, *sma1236* and *sma1239–41*) periplasmic nitrate reductase is present in this region (Figure 1). The gene *sma1250* encodes a copper-containing nitrite reductase, NirK, and is associated with a NirV-type protein which is encoded by the *nirV* gene (*sma1247*) (Figure 1). A nitric oxide reductase and a nitrous oxide reductase encoded by *norECBQD* genes (*sma1269*, *sma1272*, *sma1273*, *sma1276* and *sma1279*) and *nosRZDFYLX* genes (*sma1179*, *sma1182–86* and *sma1188*) respectively are also located in the pSymA (Figure 1). The *nos* genes have been characterized previously by Chan et al. [18] and Holloway et al. [19]. Inoculation of alfalfa plants with *S. meliloti nos* mutants did not affect the N_2 -fixing ability of the nodules, which demonstrates that *nos* genes are not essential for N_2 fixation [18,19]. The *hmp* gene is located downstream of the *nos* genes and encodes a flavohaemoglobin which has been shown recently to be involved in NO detoxification in *S. meliloti* under free-living and symbiotic conditions [20]. Genes such as *nnrU* (*sma1283*), encoding a protein which is required for expression of *nir* and *nor* genes, *azul* (*sma1243*), which encodes a blue copper protein associated with periplasmic nitrite reductase, *hemN* (*sma1266*), which encodes a protein which is involved in haem maturation, *nnrR* (*sma1245*), encoding the FNR (fumarate and nitrate reductase regulatory protein)/CRP (cAMP receptor protein)- like regulatory protein NnrR and the regulator NnrS encoded by *nnrS* gene (*sma1252*) are located on the 53 kb segment of pSymA (Figure 1). Putative genes encoding the nitrate- transport proteins NtrAB (SMa0583 and SMa0585) are located elsewhere on pSymA [17].

Transcriptomic studies have shown that O_2 limitation appears to be a key factor driving expression of *S. meliloti* denitrification genes [15]. In *S. meliloti*, expression of genes in

response to low O₂ conditions is co-ordinated via a two-component regulatory system, FixL/FixJ. Under microaerobic conditions, FixL autophosphorylates and transmits phosphate to the FixJ response regulator. Once phosphorylated, FixJ activates transcription of the *nifA* and *fixK* genes, encoding two intermediate regulators which induce expression of *fix* and *nif* genes involved in respiration and nitrogen fixation respectively [21]. FixLJ, FixK and NifA are conserved among rhizobia, but they differ in connectivity and targets. In *S. meliloti*, microaerobic transcription of denitrification genes depends on FixLJ and FixK [21]. In contrast with *B. japonicum*, where FixK₂ activates *nnrR*, the gene encoding the FNR/CRP-like regulator NnrR [22], in *S. meliloti*, *nnrR* is not a target of the FixLJ/FixK regulatory cascade in response to low O₂ conditions [21]. *S. meliloti* NnrR-

like transcriptional regulator controls *nirK* and *nor* genes, as well as other genes related to denitrification (*nap*, *nos*, *azu1*, *hemN*, *nnrU* and *nnrS*) in response to NO [20,23]. Whereas NnrR expands the FixLJ/FixK₂ regulatory cascade in *B. japonicum* [9], NnrR and FixK are part of two different NO-responsive signalling pathways in *S. meliloti* [20].

Recent findings have demonstrated that *S. meliloti* *napA* and *nirK* denitrification genes contribute about one-third to the nitric oxide generated in *Medicago truncatula* nitrogen-fixing nodules [24].

Figure 1 Genomic context of denitrification genes in the symbiotic plasmid pSymA of *S. meliloti*

O₂ requirement for denitrification by *S. meliloti*

In our studies, we have investigated the denitrification ability of *S. meliloti* under micro-oxic and anoxic conditions. Results shown in Figure 2 confirm that *S. meliloti* is unable to grow under anoxic conditions with nitrate or nitrite as terminal electron acceptors. When the cells were incubated under micro-oxic conditions (2% O₂ in the gas phase) with nitrate or nitrite in the culture medium, an increase in the attenuation at 600 nm (*D*₆₀₀) was observed, reaching a turbidity of 1.0 and 0.8 respectively, after 48 h of growth. However, in cells grown without addition of nitrate or nitrite a slight increase in *D*₆₀₀ up to 0.4 was observed after 12 h of incubation and it remained constant during the growth period. Figure 3 shows that nitrate was consumed during incubation under micro-oxic conditions, and nitrite was produced and accumulated in the incubation medium being consumed further by the cells. Maximal rates of nitrate consumption and nitrite production were observed after incubation for 24 h (Figure 3). These results suggest that, after 24 h of incubation under 2% O₂, activation of denitrification process in *S. meliloti* might take place (Figures 2 and 3). When cells were incubated under anoxic conditions with nitrate, nitrite was not detected in the growth medium (Figure 3), which confirms the inability of *S. meliloti* to denitrify under those conditions.

Figure 2 Growth of *S. meliloti* 1021 cells under micro-oxic (2% O₂) (black symbols) or anoxic (white symbols) conditions without nitrate or nitrite (triangles), and with nitrate (circles) or nitrite (squares)

OD = attenuation (*D*).

S. meliloti was able to produce N₂O (28 μmol of N₂O/mg of protein per min) when grown under micro-oxic conditions with nitrate, indicating that this bacterium is able not only to reduce nitrate to nitrite, but also to form N₂O under micro-oxic conditions. The nitrous oxide reductase enzyme is O₂ sensitive in many species. Therefore aerobic denitrification is often incomplete, and an increase in N₂O formation has been observed when conditions switch from anaerobic to aerobic [25]. However, in the case of *S. meliloti*, N₂ analyses are necessary to establish the ratio of N₂O/N₂ produced by cells grown under micro-oxic conditions with nitrate. It has been suggested that aerobic denitrification mainly occurs in environments of alternating oxic/anoxic conditions [25]. Micro-organisms capable of both aerobic and anaerobic denitrification would have the best chances of survival in those habitats [26].

Figure 3 Nitrate uptake (■) and nitrite production (Δ) under micro-oxic conditions, and nitrite production under anoxic conditions (●) for *S. meliloti*

S. meliloti 1021 cells were cultured in minimal medium with 10 mM nitrate.

Denitrification is generally accepted as an adaptive mechanism that works in anoxic environments. Usually, expression of the genes encoding the denitrifying enzymes is strictly repressed under oxic conditions, in which the bacteria can obtain sufficient energy through O₂ respiration [5]. Furthermore, post-translational inhibition by O₂ of denitrification enzymes and nitrate transport have also been reported [27,28]. However, in contrast with the strict requirement of anaerobic conditions for the expression of denitrification genes, in *S. meliloti*, some O₂ is required for the induction of denitrification. Similarly, a minimal O₂ concentration is required for denitrification by the fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* [29]. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has also been shown to perform aerobic denitrification, i.e. the

simultaneous respiration using O₂, nitrate and nitrite as terminal electron acceptors under aerobic conditions [30]. Other aerobic denitrifiers belonging to the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Alcaligenes*, *Paracoccus* and *Bacillus* have also been reported [31–34].

No direct evidence can explain why some O₂ is required for induction of denitrification in *S. meliloti*. It might be possible that O₂ is necessary for oxygenase reactions involved in the biosyntheses of essential cell components, such as sterols, haems or unsaturated fatty acids. In this context, *Paracoccus denitrificans* requires cobalamin to express a cobalamin-dependent ribonucleotide reductase, which is essential for growth only under anaerobic conditions [35]. Since denitrification and O₂ respiration are two respiratory processes associated with the membrane, then they may share some components of the respiratory chain. Thus it might be possible that both processes have to proceed simultaneously. However, the reason the reduction of nitrate must be accompanied by O₂ respiration remains to be elucidated.

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